

THE RELATION SHIP BETWEEN NURSE PERFORMANCE AND INPATIENT SATISFACTION IN THE JASMINE ROOM OF DELTA SURYA HOSPITAL, SIDOARJO

Marlita Dewi Lestari ^{1*}, Fitria Ningsih ²

¹ Lecturer of Kerta Cendekia Nursing Academy, Sidoarjo, East Java Province, Indonesia

² Delta Surya Hospital, Sidoarjo, East Java Province, Indonesia

***Correspondence:**

Marlita Dewi Lestari

Email: marlits_ok@yahoo.co.id

ABSTRACT

Background: The quality of health services is a level of service perfection that is carried out in accordance with established standards of ethics in order to increase satisfaction for each patient. Nurse performance is the work of nurses in the form of actions or practices that are easily observed or assessed. By improving the performance of nurses, the quality of service in the hospital will significantly continue to provide satisfaction to patients and the community.

Purpose: This descriptive correlational study aimed to identify the relationship between patient satisfaction and nurse's performance, especially in hospitalized patients.

Methods: A 35 hospitalized patients in Delta Surya Hospital Sidoarjo participated on this study and were assessed their perceived of nurse performance using Independent Variable questionnaire and their satisfaction level using Dependent Variable. This questionnaire instrument uses two types of statements, positive statements and negative statements, each 24 items.

Results: SPSS results that an Asymp.Sig (2-sided) value of 0,000 was seen. Because the Asymp.Sig (2-sided) value <0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between nurse performance with patient satisfaction.

Discussion: Customer satisfaction occurs when needs, wants, and their expectation can be fulfilled. And nursing services by wholeheartedly, equally regardless of rank, ethnicity, race, religion or profession will have an impact on patient satisfaction.

Key words: Patient satisfaction, nurse performance, inpatient room.

INTRODUCTION

Sometimes patients find the nurse's performance unsatisfactory, so there is a difference between expectations and the results felt. This can be seen from a number of patients who after being hospitalized in the Melati room, Delta Surya hospital in Sidoarjo. The patient said that the service in the Melati room was not satisfactory because of the nurse's poor performance, in terms of communication to the patient and

the patient's family, causing complaints to be submitted to management through a complaint card written and signed by the patient's family. Of the eight complaints related to nursing services, 5 of them complained about nursing services in the Melati room. From the survey results of service satisfaction in Melati room in August to September 2017 showed that 30% of patients expressed satisfaction, 30%

expressed satisfaction and 40% said they were dissatisfied.

From the results of a preliminary study conducted by researchers in the inpatient room in the Melati room in December 2017, data obtained for 1 (one) month in December 2017. Of the 15 respondents whose data were taken, 8 respondents (53.3%) said the nurse's performance was not good, with category 6 respondents less satisfied and 2 respondents quite satisfied, 2 respondents (13.3%) said nurse performance was good with category 1 respondent satisfied and 1 respondent very satisfied and 5 respondents (33.3%) said nurse performance was quite good with category 3 respondents satisfied and 2 respondents very satisfied.

METHODS

Study Design

The research design used is using the Analytical approach method using the Cross-Sectional design. Each research subject was only observed once and measurements were made of a character or subject variable at the time of examination.

Setting

The research location taken by the researcher is in the inpatient unit, Melati room at the Delta Surya Sidoarjo hospital.

Research Subject

The populations in this study were all patients hospitalized in the Delta Surya hospital Melati room in March, April and May 2018. The number of patients was 210 patients. Sampling in this study uses Non-Probability Sampling. And the Non-Probability Sampling technique used in this research is Purposive Sampling Technique. The sample in this study that met the Inclusion criteria was; patients are willing to be respondents and able to communicate well. While those included in the Exclusion criteria category are; patients refuse to become respondents, not able to

communicate well and decreased consciousness

After entering into the formula, the number of patients for 3 months, the results obtained 42 patients. From 42 patients after inclusion and exclusion criteria were found, 7 patients who refused to be respondents became a total sample of 35 respondents.

Instruments

The Independent Variable used in this study is the performance of the hospital nurse and measured using a questionnaire.

As for the Dependent Variable, the level of inpatient satisfaction was measured using a questionnaire that was provided by the researcher.

Questionnaire instruments include material; caring (attention), collaboration, speed, empathy, courtesy (polite attitude) and sincerity (honesty). The number of items in this questionnaire instrument are 24 items. This questionnaire instrument uses two types of statements, positive statements and negative statements. In a positive statement if the respondent answers "Very Satisfied" then given a score of 3, if the respondent answers "Satisfied" is given a score of 2, if "Dissatisfied" is given a score of 1. While in a negative statement, if the respondent answers "Very Satisfied" then given a score of 1, if the respondent answers "Satisfied" is given a score of 2 and if "Dissatisfied" is given a score of 3.

Data Analysis

Univariate Analysis aims to explain or describe the characteristics of each research variable. The form of univariate analysis depends on the type of data. For numerical data the average, median and standard deviation values are used. In general, this analysis only produces the frequency distribution and percentage of each variable. For example, the frequency distribution based on age, sex, level of

education and occupation. And then it can be continued with Bivariate Analysis. In this study using the Chi-Square statistical test. Analysis of the Chi-Square Test results from the results of this statistical test will be concluded that the relationship between these 2 variables is meaningful or not significant.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher conducted ethical clearance process and was approved by the Director of Delta Surya Hospital, Sidoarjo. Data collection procedure started with the informed consent to participants that they were briefed about the study and kept their confidentiality.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Respondents by Nurse's Performance

Table 1. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Nurse's Performance in the Melati Room of Delta Surya Hospital (n = 35).

Characteristics of Respondents	Nurse's Performance		
	Less	Enough	Well
Gender			
Man	1	1	17
Woman	2	2	12
Total	3	3	29
Age			
20-30 yr.	1	0	9
31-40 yr.	0	0	3
41-50 yr.	1	2	8
51-60 yr.	1	1	7
> 60 yr.	0	0	2
Total	3	3	29
Education			
Elementary	0	0	1
Middle	0	0	2
High	2	2	17
Bachelor	1	1	9
Total	3	3	29
Jobs			
Student	0	0	5
Government	0	0	3
Private	1	3	14
Entrepreneur	0	0	5
Doesn't Work	2	0	2
Total	3	3	29

Based on the results in the table 1, it found that the majority of respondents assume the nurse's performance is very well, as many as 29 respondents (82.86%).

Characteristics of Respondents by Patients Satisfaction Level

Table 2. Distribution of Frequency of Respondents by Patients Satisfaction Level in the Melati Room of Delta Surya Hospital (n = 35).

Characteristics of Respondents	Patient Satisfaction		
	Not Satisfied	Satisfied	Very Satisfied
Gender			
Man	1	17	1
Woman	2	13	1
Total	3	30	2
Age			
20-30 yr.	1	9	0
31-40 yr.	0	3	0
41-50 yr.	1	9	1
51-60 yr.	1	7	1
> 60 yr.	0	2	0
Total	2	30	2
Education			
Elementary	0	1	0
Middle	0	1	1
High	2	18	1
Bachelor	1	10	0
Total	3	30	2
Jobs			
Student	0	5	0
Government	0	3	0
Private	1	16	1
Entrepreneur	0	5	0
Doesn't Work	2	1	1
Total	3	30	2

Based on the results above, it found that the majority of respondents were satisfied for patient's satisfaction level, as much as 30 respondents (85.71%).

Examination of the Relationship between Nurse's Performance and Patients' Satisfaction Level in the Melati Room of Delta Surya Hospital

Table 3. Relationship between Nurse's Performance and Patients' Satisfaction Level in the Melati Room of Delta Surya Hospital (n = 35).

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	35.241 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	20.883	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	17.780	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	35		

An Asymp.Sig (2-sided) value of 0.000 was seen. Because the Asymp.Sig (2-sided) value <0.05, it can be concluded that, there is a significant relationship between nurse performance with patient satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

Based on the data, that as many as 29 respondents (82.86%) thought the nurse's performance was good, 3 respondents (8.57%) thought the nurse's performance was sufficient and 3 respondents (8.57%) thought the nurse's performance was lacking.

This can be interpreted that if the services received or felt are as expected, the performance of nurses will be assessed as good or satisfying, conversely if the quality of nurses' performance is lower than expected, the quality of service will decrease so that the impact on patient satisfaction.

There are two factors that affect performance; Internal factors, are factors related to intelligence, skills, emotional stability, personality traits, including attitudes, personality traits, physical traits, desires or motivation, age, gender,

education, work experience, cultural background and variables other personal variables.

External factors are factors that affect the performance of employees who come from the environment, including labor regulations, customer desires, competitors, economic conditions, the level of performance of nurses (Pabundu, 2006).

Next, as many as 30 respondents (85.71%) patient satisfaction was at the level of satisfaction. A total of 2 respondents (5.71%) patient satisfaction was at a very satisfied level. Customer satisfaction according to the needs model is a condition where the needs, desires and expectations of patients can be met through the products or services consumed. Therefore patient satisfaction is the ratio of quality felt by patients divided by the needs, desires and expectations of patients (Nursalam, 2014).

Customer satisfaction occurs when what you need, want, expectation of your customer can fulfill, then the customer will be satisfied. It shows that nursing services provided to patients wholeheartedly and all patients are treated equally regardless of rank, ethnicity, race, religion or profession will have an impact on patient satisfaction with nursing services provided to patients. Patients who are satisfied with the services provided by nurses will make these patients tell about their experiences being treated to family and colleagues that have an impact on increasing the visit and popularity of the hospital in the community. Judging from the frequency distribution of the relationship between the performance of nurses and patient satisfaction in the Melati room of the Delta Surya Hospital Sidoarjo, as many as 27 respondents (77.1%) nurses performed well with satisfied satisfaction levels. Nurses as one of the health workers in the hospital play an important role in efforts to achieve health development

goals. The success of health services depends on the participation of nurses in providing quality nursing care for patients (Potter & Perry, 2005).

CONCLUSION

It is known that the total respondents were 35 respondents; 29 respondents (82.9%) thought nurses' performance was good, 3 (three) respondents (8.6%) thought nurses' performance was sufficient and 3 (three) respondents (8.6%) thought nurses' performance was lacking. This shows that holistic nursing services (Spiritual Biopsychosocial) to patients respond positively. In treating patients, they do not differentiate patients by room class, but patients get the same service without seeing what room the patient occupies. It is known that the total respondents were 35 respondents; respondents who were satisfied with the performance of jasmine room nurses were 30 respondents (85.6%), 2 (two) respondents (5.7%) were very satisfied and 3 (three) respondents (8.6%) were not satisfied. It shows that nursing services provided to patients wholeheartedly and all patients are treated equally regardless of rank, ethnicity, race, religion or profession will have an impact on patient satisfaction with nursing services provided to patients. Patients who are satisfied with the services provided by nurses generally all employees in the hospital will make these patients tell about the experience in care to family and colleagues that have an impact on improving the visit and reputation of the hospital in the community. From Chi Square Test results using SPSS version 16.0 are known that there is a significant relationship between nurse performance with inpatient satisfaction in the Melati room of the Delta Surya hospital in Sidoarjo.

SUGGESTION

It is expected that health workers can provide satisfying services to patients, patients' families and visitors so that patients can share good experiences about Delta Surya hospital services to relatives and families. It is expected that the results of this study can be used as basic data in an effort to always be able to improve the quality of the performance of all nurses at Delta Surya Hospital in order to provide the best service to all customers. For further researchers related to this title, it is hoped to make the inclusion and exclusion criteria even sharper in order to obtain samples that can represent the research. It is expected that respondents with this research will have an impact on the level of patient satisfaction that increases so that the respondent's experience of the hospital gets good service.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto, S. (2006). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek* Rev. V. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Aritonang, L. R. (2005). *Kepuasan Pelanggan*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Azwar, A. (1996). *Pengantar Administrasi Kesehatan*. Jakarta: Bina Rupa Aksara.
- Azwar, S. (2009.) *Research Methods*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Khusnawati. (2010). *Analisis Kepuasan Pasien Terhadap Pelayanan pada Puskesmas Sungai Durian, Kab. Kubu Raya*. Hasanuddin Makassar University.
- Kuntoro, W., & Istiono, W. (2018). Kepuasan Pasien Terhadap Kualitas Pelayanan di Tempat Pendaftaran Pasien Rawat Jalan Puskesmas Kretek Bantul Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Kesehatan Vokasional*, 2(1), 140-147.
- Muninjaya, A.A.G. (2004). *Manajemen Kesehatan*. Jakarta: EGC.

- Notoatmojo, S. (2011). *Metodologi Penelitian Kesehatan*, Edisi kedua. *Rineka Cipta, Jakarta*.
- Nursalam. (2014). *Metodelogi Penelitian Ilmu Keperawatan*, Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
- Pabundu, T. M. (2006). *Metodologi Riset Bisnis*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
- Pohan. (2007). *Jaminan Mutu Layanan Kesehatan*. Jakarta: EGC.
- Potter, P. A., & Perry, A. G. (2005). *Buku ajar fundamental keperawatan: konsep, proses, dan praktik*.
- Sabarguna. (2004). *Quality Assurance Pelayanan Rumah Sakit*. 2nd Edition. Yogyakarta: Islam Hospital Consortium West Java-DIY.
- Sugiyono. (2012). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2012). *Reliabilitas dan Validitas* Ed. 4. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- RS Woodward Palu. (2013). *Profil RS Woodward Palu Tahun 2013*.
- Taufiq. (2015). *Manajemen Mutu Perusahaan*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.